

Impact of afforestation policy on vegetation greenness in China

Wentong Xie^{*1,2}, Yong Ge^{†1}, Nicholas Hamm^{‡2}, Giles Foody^{§3}

¹Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research, Chinese Academy of Science, Beijing, 100101, China.

²School of Geographical Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering, University of Nottingham, Ningbo, 315100, China

³School of Geography, University of Nottingham, University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, United Kingdom

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Summary

Understanding the spatiotemporal change of greenness and the main driving factors affecting greenness can provide an effective theoretical basis for ecological environment protection and restoration in China. Based on the data of 2853 counties and the Leaf Area Index (LAI) from 2000 to 2020, we used the Bayesian spatio-temporal model to quantify the spatial-temporal change of greenness and a fixed-effects model was used to investigate the effects of the environmental protection policy in China. The results show that greenness has increased because of afforestation policy but impacted by population and climate change.

KEYWORDS: Greenness, Influencing-factors, Policy, Fixed-effect model

1. Introduction

The Earth's vegetation coverage is a manifestation of the ecological environmental condition. The most common way of measuring it is by using an index that describes the relative "greenness" (a comparison of amounts of visible and near-infrared sunlight that are absorbed and reflected by plants) of the Earth's vegetation (Mayhew, 2009). Leaf area index (LAI) is a well-defined physical attribute of vegetation to represent it. Climate factors can provide necessary growth conditions for vegetation growth, dominate the vegetation change process in a large scale. Afforestation policy is a large-scale policy that aims to improve the regional vegetation coverage directly.

Recent research shows that 60% of vegetation greening in China in the period 2000 to 2017 is due to human intervention (Chen et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2016). The vegetation change in Inner Mongolia is mainly affected by human activities in the recent ten years, with a relative contribution rate of 85% (Sun, Yang, Zhang, & Wang, 2015). Wang et al. (2019) calculated the anthropogenic impacts of vegetation cover in China from 2001 to 2015 based on NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) data. The results showed that the human activities impact decrease slightly, and the area of negative impacts was larger than that of positive impacts. The degree of human-induced land degradation tends to be reduced by precipitation (Huang, Li, Wu, & Pei, 2012).

Therefore, it is necessary to study the relationship between vegetation, climate and human activities, in order to better explain the process of terrestrial ecosystem change and its impact mechanism.

* xiewt@igsnr.ac.cn

† gey@igsnr.ac.cn

‡ Nicholas.Hamm@nottingham.edu.cn

§ Giles.Foody@nottingham.ac.uk

2. Data and study area

The study area of this work is mainland China (**Figure 1**). LAI data was from the MODIS LAI product, MCD15A3H.006 (500 m spatial resolution, 4-day temporal resolution). Temperature and precipitation data used in this work were collected from Resource and Environment Science and Data Center, Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research, CAS (<http://www.resdc.cn/>). Population data was collected from *China Statistical Yearbook (County-level)*, and the afforestation data was collected from *China forestry statistical yearbook*. (<https://data.cnki.net/Yearbook>). These data are aggregated to provide annual averages at the county administrative level.

Figure 1. Study area

3. Methodology

3.1 Random-effect model

Fixed effects and random effects models are both applicable to research questions with complex structure, including place-based hierarchies, and temporal hierarchies, in which measurement occasions are within entities such as individuals within countries. A Random-effect model would be Equation 1:

$$G_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{t=2000}^{2020} a_y P_{it} + bS_{it} + cH_{it} + dT_{it} + eR_{it} + \mu_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where i represents the i th county and t represents the year ($t = 2000-2020$). G_{ij} is the dependent variable expressed by LAI value, β_0 is the intercept term, including $P_{it}, S_{it}, H_{it}, T_{it}, R_{it}$. The implementation of afforestation policy is expressed by the dummy variable P_{it} . $P_{it} = 1$ indicates that i th county has implemented it in the t year, and $P_{it} = 0$ indicates that the i th county has not implemented it in the t year. The socio-economic factors include S_{it} of population and H_{it} of afforestation area in county i in the t year. Climate factors include annual mean temperature T_{it} and annual mean precipitation R_{it} . a, b, c, d, e are the coefficients of the series of covariates. The ‘random’ part of the model consists of μ_{it} , and ε_{it} is the occasion-level residual for year t of county i .

3.2 Fixed-effect model

Fixed effect model means that the influence of omitted variables on explained variables in different time periods is fixed (Sun Hongyu, 1998). It is widely used in economic research (Huang Q, Rozelle S, 2006; Liu, 2008). Since afforestation policy is the key research factor, the fixed effect model is used to quantitatively analyze the impact of afforestation policy on greenness status in China, and the applicability of the model needs to be tested by Hausman. The formula is expressed as Equation 2:

$$G_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{t=2000}^{2020} a_y P_{it} + bS_{it} + cH_{it} + dT_{it} + eR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, G_{ij} , β_0 , P_{it} , S_{it} , H_{it} , T_{it} , R_{it} , ε_{it} , a_y , b , c , d , and e have same definition with Equation 1.

4. Results

The Hausmann test is used to determine whether the fixed effect model is more suitable than the random effect model. According to the results, the Hausmann test shows that $\chi^2 = 135.94$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (random-effect model is suitable), the fixed effect model should be the used.

It can be seen from **Table 1** that the afforestation policy improves the LAI value, which is conducive to improving the greenness status. The results showed that the coefficients of the afforestation policy variable, precipitation and temperature were positive and significantly different from zero ($p\text{-value} < 0.01$). This indicates that, as this variable increase, LAI also increases. The coefficient of the population variable is negative and significantly different from zero ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). This suggests that population pressure leads to lower LAI and hence the reduction of vegetation cover.

Table 1. The effects of factors on greenness in all counties in China

Variable	Coefficient	t
Afforestation	0.2660***	0.0096
Population	-0.0120**	0.0002
Precipitation	0.2830***	0.0002
Temperature	0.1430***	0.0009
constant	0.3919***	0.1300
Fixed effect test of FX (time)	Yes	
Fixed effect test of FX (counties)	Yes	
Observation	2853	
R ²	0.4549	

Note: *** indicates significant at 0.01 level. ** indicates significant at 0.05 level. * Indicates significant at 0.1 level.

5. Conclusion and Discussion

This study investigated the effectiveness of afforestation policy in the change of vegetation greenness in China between 2000 and 2020. The results show that China's greenness has increased under the implementation of artificial afforestation policy, but the effectiveness of the policy is offset by other factor such as population. Climate factors such as temperature and precipitation have a significant impact on vegetation productivity. For the quantifying policy, this study used the afforestation area of each county to represent policy variable. About the discussion between fixed-effect model and random-effect model, usually, if the assumption is correct, RE would be the preferred choice because of its greater flexibility and generalizability, and its ability to model context. (Bell & Jones, 2015). If the data is sampled, random effects could be preferred. On the contrary, and the fixed effect could be used. Therefore, according to the situation of this study, and follow-up work of the study takes into account to divide China into different regions, for example ecological policy implementation areas and non-implementation areas, poverty areas and non-poverty areas, the fixed effect model was preferred.

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Biographies

Wentong XIE is PhD student of joint PhD program between University of Nottingham and IGSNRR. She focuses on geo-spatial, spatial-temporal statistics applied in ecological environment, poverty issues and the driving factors analysis.

GE Yong is a professor of geographical information science at Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research (IGSNRR), Chinese Academy of Sciences. Her research interests broadly focus on the statistical aspects of spatial and spatio-temporal data. Her research topics range from spatial-temporal sampling, scaling, and spatial data quality.

Dr Nicholas Hamm is an associate professor in the School of Geographical Sciences at the University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China. His research interests are in geospatial data science – in particular geostatistics, geospatial uncertainty and spatial data quality.

Giles Foody is Professor of Geographical Information Science at the University of Nottingham. His main interests lie at the interface of remote sensing, informatics, and environmental science.